

**Liberating Indian Women from Slavery: An Analysis of Dr.
Ambedkar's Contribution for Uplifting Indian Women's Rights**

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Abstract:

In the long history of humanity and its development, woman has always been as vital as man, yet she has always been looked down upon as an inferior creature. This position of women, throughout the ages, prevails not only in family and society but also in the matters of privileges and rights. In India, Women's condition had been much better in Indus Valley civilization which itself was a matriarchal civilization. They enjoyed many privileges even in early Vedic period. But in later Vedic period, their condition started deteriorating due to the imposition of various unnecessary moral and religious laws. Hindu lawgiver, Manu, added fuel to fire when he codified all such laws with many more in *Manusmiriti*, a dominant law book on social, religious and moral values. Women's condition had gone through a radical change from worse to worst with Muslim invasion. In view of this pathetic condition of Indian women, many social reformers tried their best to elevate women's condition in the society. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar was one of them. He has done a pioneering work to improve the status of women in Indian society. This research paper is an endeavor to seek the contribution of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar for the upliftment of Indian women's rights.

Keywords: Matriarchal, Dominant, Radical, Upliftment, Pathetic, Religious.

“I measure the progress of a community by the degree of progress which women have achieved”

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar

Women comprise almost half of the human population of the world. No development can be thought without their help and support. They have been given proper place in scriptures and considered as the Ardhagini of the man. The worship of God cannot be completed without their participation. Almost all the popular religions of the world have given sufficient importance to women. In spite of this, they have not achieved their due place in various spheres of life, viz. socio-political, economic and educational. It shows our false claim that we have been respecting women since the dawn of ancient civilization. It becomes evident when we cast our eyes on the discriminatory behaviour against women, and double standard of religious morality for male and female.

When Hindu lawgiver Manu says, “yatr naryasto pojyantay, ramantay tatr devta [3/56] (where women are provided place of honor, gods are pleased and reside there in that household)”, he uplifted the women to a great height but in the same law book, at different places, he has bitterly criticized women. In Christianity, the first woman, Eve is represented as the sinner of mankind. It is Eve who had eaten the fruit of the forbidden tree due to which humankind had to come on the earth for penance. Islam has also created so many discriminatory rules for women. The main reason for the subjugation of women is these laws and their inflexible behavior. It is believed that these scriptures have been composed by the inspiration of Almighty or He himself has created them, therefore, they are unchangeable. The rigidity of these scriptures plays a vital role in women’s suppression because, before the formation of the written constitution, these scriptures used to be the law books and none could have jumped their boundary. Since then, such religious ethos has been embedded in women’s mind through patriarchal ideology. In our postmodern world, when almost all the developed and developing nations of the world have their own written constitutions which guarantee the equal rights for the women in all the sphere of life, there is a great clamor about women’s rights which shows that women’s causes have not been adequately addressed. Most of the women are being suppressed because the society is still ruled by those unnecessary religious dogmas instead of written constitution. They do not dare to put a step ahead to rule out such discriminatory laws due to their ignorance or pseudo-knowledge.

When we throw light on the status of women in India since the Pre-Vedic period, we find out that our Indus Valley civilization had been matriarchal and women were given due importance in almost every area of human activity. Traces of such societies were found in the excavation of various prominent cities of Indus Valley civilization. Rahul Sankrutayan, a very famous traveler and writer of Hindi literature, referred to such matriarchal families in his book

From Olga to Ganga. With the advent of the Aryans the matriarchal society was replaced by the patriarchal society in our country. The Aryan culture in India is known as the Vedic culture which is divided into two parts for the convenience of the study i.e. the early and the later Vedic period. In the early-Vedic period women were entitled to almost all sorts of necessary rights which are essential for human being. The women had access to all branches of learning. They played an important role in religious ceremonies. The girls were free to choose their life partners through Swayambara system. All the fields of learning including the study of Vedas were open to women and they were eligible for Upanayanam Ceremony. They had equal right to annul a marriage or they could opt for remarriage. Even widow marriage was in vogue. According to Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, even during Kautilyas' time, women lived with dignity.

In later Vedic period, the condition of women had started deteriorating through gender discrimination. The social status of women was undermined, many restrictions were imposed on them, and they were deprived of basic human amenities. Not only the women but also the majority of the population including the Shudras and Atishudras i.e. the aborigines of India had also faced discriminatory behaviour in this age. This dissatisfaction had led them to join the Buddhism which guaranteed them equal rights. By this time, Hindu lawgiver, Manu had also introduced his book, Manusmriti, a book on social code of conduct. In this book, he had codified all those prevalent social evils as social ethos instead of their eradication. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar, after meditating over this book, stated that the emergence of real evil practices like child marriages for girls, ban on widow remarriage, several rules of widowhood and sati, occurred during Manu Smriti era. Many other Brahmanical scriptures including epics, Smritis, Puranas etc. and various ancient Indian dynasties such as Gupta dynasty, Shung dynasty etc. which adhered such rules, had also deteriorated women's position in the society. Women's condition had gone through a radical change from worse to worst with Muslim invasion. They had brought various social evils like Purdah system, polygamy and misogynistic Talak system in India. Nevertheless, this period had produced some powerful women rulers like Razia Sultana and Noorjahan.

With the arrival of the Britishers in India, a new era of social reformation had been started. The introduction of the western education had enlightened many Indians who had started to purify the Hindu society from its evils. Swami Vivekananda and Raja Ram Mohan Roy worked hard for the abolition of the Sati system. They were the ardent supporters of re-marriage. Jyotiba Phule and his wife Savitri Bai Phule had sacrificed their lives for the education of girls. Periyar E.V.Ramaswami pleaded for the rights of women especially in the self-respect marriage formula. Many other social reformers like Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar, Swami Dayanand

Saraswati, Mahatma Gandhi, Justice Mahadev Govind Ranade, Sir Syed Ahmed Khan etc. had also contributed their best for the cause of women's liberation.

Without an iota of doubt it can be claimed that the relentless efforts of these social reformers had paved the way to elevate the status of women. But nature was anxiously waiting for a hero who could equalize the position of man and woman with a pragmatic approach and that hero appeared on the Indian scene as Dr. B.R. Ambedkar. He followed the path of Mahatma Jyotiba Phule who led him to the weakest among the weak. He adhered the basic laws of social life, i.e. liberty, equality and fraternity irrespective of the caste, class, religion and gender. Right from the days of *Mook Nayak* and *Bahishkrit Bharat*, oppression of women remained a major plank of Dr. Ambedkar's movement. He involved women in all his social struggles.

Reformative Steps Taken by Dr. B.R. Ambedkar

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar had very well seen the deplorable condition of the Indian women, so he had made his best efforts to liberate them from various social and religious ties. With the help of his intuitive knowledge, he has systematically attacked on various social evils. The writings and speeches of Ambedkar show what values India should develop and how they would modernize its social and political institutions. Ambedkar saw women as the victims of the oppressive, caste-based and rigid hierarchical social system. He has taken the following reformatory steps to improve the women's position in India.

Women and Constitutional Rights

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar has given equal status to women at par with men by providing many provisions in the Constitution. He incorporated the values of liberty, equality and fraternity in the Indian Constitution. V.R. Krishna Iyer is of the view that the constitution quickened by social conscience, has added invincible legal missiles for women's liberation. Our Constitution, in its preamble, guarantees:

- Social, economic and political justice
- Freedom of thoughts, expression, belief, faith and worship
- Equality of status and opportunity
- Fraternity, assuring the dignity of the individual and national unity to all the citizens of India without any discrimination of caste, creed or sex.

A number of articles in the Constitution help the women to improve their status and to compete with their male counterparts. This is evident from different provisions of Indian Constitution:

- Article 14 guarantees that the State shall not deny equality before the law and equal protection of the laws within the territory of India.

Indexed, Peer Reviewed & Refereed Journal

- Article 15 prohibits discrimination against any citizen on the ground of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth.
- Article 15 (3) empowers the State to make positive discrimination in favour of women and children.
- Article 16 provides equality of opportunity in matters of public employment.
- Article 23 prohibits trafficking of human beings and forced labour.
- Article 39 (a) and (d) enjoins the State to provide equal means of livelihood and equal pay for equal work.
- Article 42 enjoins the State to make provisions for securing just and humane conditions of work, and for maternity relief.
- Article 51A (e) imposes a Fundamental Duty on every citizen to renounce the practices derogatory to the dignity of women.
- Article 243D (3) makes a provision that not less than 1/3rd of the total number of seats to be filled by direct election in every Panchayat shall be reserved for women, and such seats would be allotted by rotation to different constituencies in a Panchayat.
- Article 243T(3) makes a provision that not less than 1/3rd of the total number of seats to be filled by direct election in every Municipality shall be reserved for women and such seats would be allotted by rotation to different constituencies in a Municipality.
- Article 243T (4) provides reservation to the offices of Chairpersons in Municipalities for SC, ST, Women in such manner as the legislature of a State may, by law, provide.

In pursuance of the above Constitutional provisions, various legislative enactments have been framed to protect, safeguard and promote the welfare of women.

Hindu Code Bill

One of the most important contributions of Dr. B.R.Ambedkar in relation to the elevation of the status of women in India was his initiative to draft and introduce the Hindu Code Bill in the Constituent Assembly on 24th of February, 1949. Being India's first Law Minister and Chairman of the Drafting Committee of the Constituent Assembly, he thought it appropriate to liberate women from the age old bondage of slavery by reforming the Hindu social laws created by Manu. The modern manifesto of the women's liberation, the Hindu Code Bill, sought among many other reforms, to put an end to a variety of marriage systems prevailing in India and legalize only monogamous marriages. The Code also sought to confer on women the right to property and adaptation which have been denied by Manu. It put men and women on an equal level in all legal matters.

The Hindu Code Bill contained new progressive rules on seven different matters; i.e. (1) the right to property of a deceased Hindu who has died intestate without making a will, to both male and female (2) the order of succession among the different heirs to property to a deceased dying intestate (3) the law of maintenance (4) marriage (5) divorce (6) adaptation and (7) minority and guardianship.

Dr. Ambedkar pointed out that the ideals enshrined in the Bill, are derived from the Constitution based on equality, liberty and fraternity. He also said that the original Indian society was not based on caste system and women's oppression. Women had equal share in property with men. After the emergence of Brahmanic literature at the subsequent stages, they were totally deprived of property rights. He pointed out that the sacramental marriage does not satisfy the ideals of equality or liberty. The Indian sacramental marriage was described by him as polygamy for men and perpetual slavery for women. He stressed that women should have the freedom to break the contract of such marriages. He insisted that constitutional commitment to liberty and equality did not permit the restoration of discriminatory ancient and archaic ideals. In short, all the provisions of the Bill were aimed at providing a legal framework for social change. But the resistance from orthodox Hindus inside and outside of the Parliament was so strong that progressive and liberal approach of Dr. Ambedkar was defeated and he felt compelled to resign from then Nehru Cabinet of Ministers.

Besides providing constitutional guarantee of equality to women, Ambedkar introduced and got four powerful acts passed to strengthen the position of women in the society. These were also incorporated in the Hindu code Bill. They are:

(1)The Hindu Marriage Act, 1955, which was amended in 1976, makes the following provisions for women:

- (a) Marriageable age of females raised to 18 years (sec. 5).
- (b) The legitimization of illegitimate children (sec. 16).
- (c) Punishment of bigamy (sec. 17).
- (d) Provision for alimony (sec. 25).
- (e) Custody of children (sec. 26).

(2)The Hindu succession Act, 1956, which makes following provisions for women:

- (a) A widow has a right to adopt a son or a daughter (sec. 8).
- (b) It also provides an opportunity to a female Hindu to be independent and disposed of her property by will as she wishes and desires (sec.14).

- (c) A uniform scheme of succession to the property of a Hindu female, who dies, intestate after commencement of the Act, is made in section 15. Previously under the uncodified law the succession to Stridhan varied according to the marital status of a woman.

(3)The Hindu minority and Guardianship Act, 1956, which makes following provisions for women:

- (a) Natural guardians of a Hindu minor in the case of a boy or an unmarried girl—the father, and after him, the mother but the custody of a minor who has not completed the age of five years shall ordinarily be with the mother (sec. 6 a).
- (b) In case of an illegitimate boy or an illegitimate unmarried girl—the natural guardian would be the mother, and after her, the father (sec. 6 b).
- (c) The mother is empowered to change the guardian, appointed by the father and may appoint a new guardian by will {sec. 9 (3, 4)}.

(4)The Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956, which makes following provisions for women:

- (a) This Act accepts adoption of a male and a female child without any difference. Prior to this, a daughter could not be adopted.
- (b) In the uncodified law a spinster or a widow had no right to adopt whereas this Act grants them the right to adopt (sec. 8).
- (c) Under the old Hindu Law a wife was not consulted while adopting a child or while giving a child for adoption, whereas this Act made it compulsory to consult her in both the cases (sec. 9).
- (d) Section 11(3) lays down that, a father should adopt a daughter at least 21 years younger to him.
- (e) Section 18 of this act provides many laws regarding maintenance of a Hindu wife.

Apart from the above mentioned provisions, he has formed many more laws for Indian women to help them to lead a dignified life. From the foregone discussion, it is crystal clear that Baba Saheb Ambedkar's contribution to the upliftment of the status of women in India through legislative actions is highly appreciable and commendable.

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